

Impact of additional STR loci and maternal inclusion on the accuracy of duo and trio paternity tests: A comparative study

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Abstract

Paternity testing is a critical tool in forensic science, often utilised to resolve disputes, establish familial relationships in criminal investigations, and provide evidence in cases of inheritance, custody, or immigration. This study evaluates the impact of using additional STR markers and the inclusion of maternal DNA on the accuracy of paternity testing. The Verifiler™ and Identifiler™ kits were compared in duo (child and putative father) and trio (child, mother, and putative father) paternity tests. Findings indicate that the use of additional markers and the inclusion of maternal DNA significantly enhance the accuracy of paternity testing, reducing the likelihood of false inclusions and exclusions, particularly in duo scenarios. Results show that duo tests, which omit maternal DNA, are more susceptible to errors, especially when fewer markers are analysed. Including the mother and utilising a comprehensive marker set, such as those provided by Verifiler™, improves the reliability of paternity outcomes and minimises the risk of incorrect conclusions. This study recommends duo testing only when absolutely necessary, with the highest possible number of markers employed to ensure reliable results. These findings contribute to the ongoing improvement of paternity testing methodologies, particularly for complex relationships and high-stakes legal cases.

Keywords

Paternity testing, STR markers, Verifiler™, Identifiler™, forensic genetics

1. Introduction

Paternity testing is crucial in forensic applications, resolving legal disputes, identifying familial relationships in criminal investigations, and providing evidence in inheritance, custody, or immigration cases [1]. Early paternity testing used ABO blood group variations, polymorphic proteins, and enzymes, followed by advances with human lymphocyte antigens (HLA). The discovery of hypervariable short tandem repeats (STRs) revolutionised genetic analysis accuracy, a capability that has grown with expanding multiplex PCR kits [2].

DNA paternity testing ideally analyses the mother's and father's alleles at specific STR regions to determine the parental origin of a child's alleles, based on Mendel's laws of inheritance. Duo paternity tests involve only the child and putative father, whereas trio tests include the mother's DNA. With increased demand for duo (motherless) tests, reduced specificity arises since maternal alleles cannot be confirmed without her DNA [3]. Mutations further complicate the interpretation, increasing the likelihood of errors.

Previous studies have explored false inclusions in duo tests [4-5], but false exclusions have received less attention. Given the significant impact of paternity testing, such as in custody cases, false inclusions can be catastrophic. While research has examined the effects of using fewer markers in paternity testing [6-7], this study aims to evaluate the impact of additional STR markers and maternal DNA inclusion on the accuracy of paternity testing. Specifically, it compares the Verifiler™ and Identifiler™ kits in duo and trio tests, assessing differences in Combined Paternity Index (CPI) values, false inclusions, and false exclusions.

2. Material studied, methods, techniques

2.1 DNA profiling

Buccal swabs were collected from 213 cases (156 paternity inclusions and 57 paternity exclusions) previously identified through trio paternity testing. DNA was extracted from all buccal swabs using the Prep-n-Go™ Buffer (Applied Biosystems™) [8]. STR profiling was conducted using the validated reduced-volume PCR method with both the AmpFℓSTR™ Identifiler™ PCR Amplification Kit (Applied Biosystems™), which targets 15 STR loci [9], and the Verifiler™ Express PCR Amplification Kit (Applied Biosystems™), which targets 23 STR loci [10]. Capillary electrophoresis was performed on the ABI Prism® 3500xL Genetic Analyzer

(Applied Biosystems™) according to the manufacturer’s instructions, and profile confirmation was conducted using GeneMapper® ID-X v1.6 software (Applied Biosystems™).

2.2 Statistical analysis

The CPI was calculated for both duo and trio paternity scenarios using both kits, with calculations performed on Converge™ Software (Applied Biosystems™), with an internal inclusion acceptance threshold of 10,000 CPI for Verifiler™, and 1,000 CPI for Identifiler™. Significant differences were assessed using a paired t-test, with a p-value threshold set at 0.05.

3. Results

3.1 Inclusion cases

As expected, a positive correlation was identified between the number of loci tested and the CPI in both duo and trio paternity inclusion tests (Figure 1). The paired t-test revealed no significant difference (p-value = 0.067) between the trio paternity tests carried out with both kits. However, a notable difference (p-value = 0.031) was found between the duo paternity tests when additional loci were analysed.

Figure 1: A violin plot presenting the distribution of CPIs in duo and trio tests using both Verifiler™ and Identifiler™ kits.

Using the Verifiler™ kit, the number of cases with CPIs below the acceptance threshold increased from zero to two when the mother was not included. Both of these cases involved mutations, as discussed below. The Identifiler™ kit showed a more pronounced effect, with one case below the threshold in trio tests and a significant rise to eight cases below the threshold in duo tests. Of these, the trio case involved a mutation, whereas only three of the eight duo cases had mutations.

3.2 Exclusion cases

In the exclusion cases, a notable difference was observed between the two kits in duo paternity tests (Figure 2). One of the cases presented only one mismatch with Identifiler™ in a duo test, but this increased to three mismatches with Verifiler™. By including the mother’s DNA in a trio test for this case, three mismatches were found with Identifiler™, and seven mismatches with Verifiler™. This demonstrates the importance of including the mother in paternity tests and also the value of additional markers in confidently excluding a putative father. Additionally, when comparing duo paternity tests using Verifiler™ to those using Identifiler™, the average reduction in the number of incompatible loci was 4.4 loci.

Figure 2: A bar chart displaying the frequency of mismatches in excluded cases in duo tests using both Verifiler™ and Identifiler™ kits.

3.3 Mutations

In paternity testing using STR markers, a mutation refers to a genetic change where the number of repeat units at an STR locus differs between a child and their biological parent. It is considered good practice to assign a mutation when both parents are tested, as testing only one parent could lead to misidentifying a mismatch as an inconsistent allele rather than a mutation, especially in cases involving closely related parents or when a close relative of the putative parent is the biological parent [11]. This can be clarified by including both parents or adding more markers.

In this study, nine mutations were identified: five from the father, two from the mother, and two of undetermined origin. All cases involving paternal mutations produced the lowest CPIs in all types of paternity tests. Considering mismatches as mutations, duo tests using Verifiler™ resulted in CPIs below the inclusion threshold of 10,000 CPI in two cases (392.23 with a one-step deletion at D18S51, and 5,115.94 with a one-step insertion at FGA). This effect was amplified with fewer markers analysed using Identifiler™, where three duo tests fell below the 1,000 CPI threshold, with CPIs of 1.14, 20.80, and 20.21 (the latter involving a one-step mutation of unknown origin at vWA).

Discussion

The significant difference between the duo tests using Verifiler™ and Identifiler™ kits highlights the impact of additional markers on the CPI of these tests. When fewer STRs are analysed, there is a reduction in incompatible loci from excluded cases, with an average reduction of 4.4 loci in this study. Without the mother's DNA, this reduction increases the possibility of wrongful inclusion and exclusion, and this risk is further increased when fewer loci are analysed. This could also be an issue when the mother and father of a child are related, which is common in South Asia through consanguineous marriages between cousins [12]. Such situations could cause issues in immigration cases, where, without the inclusion of the mother and with fewer STRs analysed, there could be a possibility of false inclusion of the putative father, even if he is related to the child but is not the biological father [13]. As shown in this study, adding extra markers to the testing reduces the likelihood of such errors.

Furthermore, the number of cases dropping below each kit's threshold provides valuable insight into the probability of a case being reported as inconclusive

or wrongfully excluded. The fact that the percentage of cases below the threshold in duos decreased from 5.13% with Identifiler™ to 1.28% with Verifiler™ highlights the advantage of additional markers. While not as pronounced, this effect is also mirrored in the trios, with no cases below the threshold with Verifiler™, while 0.64% of cases below the threshold with Identifiler™. In both cases, the increase in cases below the threshold when the mother was not included in the test reveals a key downside of duo paternity tests. While the difference is not drastic between the Verifiler™ trios and duos or between the Verifiler™ trios and the Identifiler™ trios, it remains true that only the Verifiler™ trios experienced no cases dropping below the assigned threshold.

Additionally, when Identifiler™ was used in a duo test on a previously excluded case, only one incompatible locus was identified, increasing the risk of incorrectly attributing this incompatibility to a mutation. The additional markers provided by the Verifiler™ kit increased the number of incompatible loci in this case to three, a number that would prompt further investigation, including statistical evaluation, the addition of more markers, or including the mother in the test, before making a decision on inclusion or exclusion.

While all the data in this study suggest that using more markers and including both parents in the test produces the ideal results, compromising on just one of these variables, if necessary, would not significantly increase the likelihood of a false result. However, as supported by Zhang et al. [14] and Gao et al. [15], using fewer markers and excluding the mother from the test is not recommended.

Conclusion

This study highlights the impact of additional STR markers and maternal DNA inclusion in paternity testing, emphasising the importance of comprehensive approaches for accuracy. Comparing Verifiler™ and Identifiler™ kits shows that extra markers significantly reduce false inclusions or exclusions, particularly in duo tests, which are more error-prone without maternal DNA.

Including both parents and using comprehensive marker sets, like Verifiler™, enhances confidence by reducing ambiguity and minimising errors. This is crucial in cases involving related parents or complex immigration scenarios, where mistakes can have serious consequences.

The study supports duo testing only when necessary, recommending the use of as many markers as possible for reliability. Further research into marker

count, family relationships, and mutation rates will improve paternity testing and mitigate risks.

Conflict of interest statement

All claims in this article are solely those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect their affiliated company or organisation.

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